

DROUGHT TRIGGERS FOREST FIRES: IMPACTS, SOLUTIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

Drought is a natural disaster that can have fatal consequences and cause death. Trees and grasses, which are common wildfire fuels, may become drier and more combustible during drought conditions. A major factor in the rise in the likelihood and size of wildfires has been climate change, which includes rising temperatures, protracted droughts, and a thirsty environment. In continents of the world rich with forests, drought is a leading cause of wildfires and these fires can have multiple environmental impacts and tackling with these fires once they are triggered is very difficult and it left everything destroyed. In this Chapter, we have talked about the unfavourable environmental impacts of forest fires and also the solutions and preventive measures to tackle with wildfires triggered by droughts. We have also talked about the role of technology in mitigation of droughts and forest fires to avoid the adverse consequences.

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INTRODUCTION

A drought is a prolonged dry season that can occur across the world according to the natural climatic cycle. It is a catastrophe that comes about gradually and is characterized by a shortage of rain, which results in a water shortage (WHO, 2019). A forest fire is an uncontrolled fire that starts in foliage that is taller than 1.8 meters (6 feet). These fires frequently expand to the magnitude of a massive inferno and are occasionally sparked by fire and fuel from surface and the ground fires.(WHO, 2019).

During drought circumstances, wildfire fuels like trees and grasses may dry up and grow more flammable. Drought can increase both the risk of a spark and the rate when a fire spreads. Similarly, (Linsley et al. (1975) defined A hydrologic drought is described in a typical textbook as “a period throughout when stream flows are inadequate to supply recognized uses under a particular water-management system.”

One of the main challenges to conducting an efficient examination of these phenomena, according to

Yevjevich (1967), is the scarcity of a clear and accurate description of droughts. The island of Bali, any stretch of time without rain that lasts 6 days or longer is regarded as a drought. The country Libya has droughts are only acknowledged after two years. (Hudson and Hazen, 1964)

In many ecosystems, prolonged droughts enhance the risk of fires. Wildfires brought on by drought periodically release gaseous and particulate forms of carbon and nutrients into the environment. (Raison et al. 1985) as well as by runoff erosion and leaching (Dunnette et al., 2014) waters. Despite upsets of C and nutrients from greenery, wildfires cause biogeochemical changes that frequently boost the availability of nutrients in soils. Soils (Wan et al., 2001; Raison, 1979).

Nutrient binding In soil and vegetation, Combustion releases organic stuff the addition of adding soil-based inorganic K, as well as magnesium, calcium, and P and N. The oxidation of increases soil NH₄ levels. Ash

inputs, organic material, and nitrogen (N) release from clay interchange locations between layers. Typical post fire soil NH_4 stays high for almost a year, which is carried out by an increase in NO_3 in soil (Certini, 2005).

Forest fires do significant harm to the ecosystem; they also have detrimental effects on the atmosphere, hydrosphere, and lithosphere as well as on species. Additionally, the annual economic cost of forest fires is projected to be in the billions of rubles. Additionally, forest fires can result in fatalities, particularly if they spread quickly to a populous area. Smoke from fires has a negative impact on people's health. (Bartenev et al. 2018) (Kasymov et al. 2017). Almost always, forest fires begin on the ground. When a fire breaks out for any reason, mosses, lichens, forest debris, and downed trees start to ignite. Young growth then, undergrowth, and, in ideal circumstances, the mother's canopy's crowns burn. If peat or humus levels are in the fire's path. They are capable of drowning fire. Only lightning-related fires typically start with the trees themselves on fire (Usatin I P 2011) (Morkovina et al. 2015).

1. Environmental Impact of Forest Fire

Forest fire have an adverse effect on our surrounding environment because due to the relative ease which have a large amount of hazardous compound can spread to the nearby environment. Forest fires that have had significant negative impacts on the ecosystem and environment where initiatives have been made to remediate such consequences. It is

important to understand about these compounds that have directly effects on the three main environmental components that are atmosphere, aquatic environment and terrestrial life need to be recognized and understood (Simonson et al. 2001).

The effects of the fire effluents on the ecosystem will depend on the length duration of exposure and the way of getting to the environment. It is a clear difference between short term impacts and long term impacts is a way to distinguish impacts on environment.

The majority of **short-term effects** are thought to happen during a few days or a few hours. This condition is predicted duration that is recorded, and it must at the very least list the following contaminants (Marlair et al. 2004);

- Metals
- Particulate
- Sulphur oxides (SO_x)
- Nitrogen oxides (NO_x)
- Halogenated acids (HX)

The **long-term environmental effects** brought on by fire dangers will be regarded as effects that are not immediately felt or understood. These contaminants have been recognized that are as follow (EPA 2008);

- Metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their long-term effects.
- Polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDF) and Aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH).
- Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB) and Polybrominated dibenzodioxins (PBDD).

Figure 1: Wildfire impact on environment

The clear geographical distribution of forest and forest growing condition in **Russia Far Forest** that cause the high burning ability of forest. The patterns and roles that are followed for forest fires in the development and recover of forest vegetation as well as their role to world processes can be studied using this region as an appropriate model. Wildfires have been traditionally the primary determinant of forest forming and their producing processes as well as characteristics of succession regularities in the Far East.

For the period of time it is observed that Khabarovsk Krai experienced the effects of devastating forest fires. We specifically noticed the catastrophic forest fire occurrence during the past 40 years in 1976, 1988, and 1998, or every 10 to 12 years. A significant detrimental impact of forest fires on the entire forest fund region, particularly local forest areas threatened by frequent forest fires. Total 1,314 forest fires that occurred in Khabarovsk Krai effected 3% of the total

area covered by the forest fund. There were a lot of fires across an area of about 15 million acres. Significant sections have almost completely vanished their organ genic layers of soil due to the fire's severe ferocity (Kulikov et al. 1998).

1.1. Effect of Wildfire On Soil Properties

Forest fire strongly affecting the soil biologically, chemically, and physically (Panico et al. 2020). The changes that take place during the flare are caused immediately by the distribution of the heat by the combustion of biomass within the soil and on the surface (O'Brien et al. 2018). The severity of a fire, which is determined by its intensity, length, and frequency, has an impact on the qualities of the soil (Lucas-Borja et al. 2020). The temperature of the soil during burning determines how the properties of the soil are altered as demonstrated and damage the properties of soil, such as its vegetative matter and moisture content (Sazawa et al. 2018).

Figure 2: Effect of Wildfire On Soil Properties

1.2. Biological, Physical and Chemical properties of soil

There are some properties of soil that are affected of forest fire are as follow:

1.2.1. Biological Properties

The biological features of the soil i.e microorganisms, biota activities and communities, soil invertebrates fluctuate when soils are heated by wildfires or controlled burns. Fire immediately kills or denaturates soil microorganisms by combustion, or it can cause other types of biological damage (Knelman et al. 2015). The fact that fine roots, bacteria, fungi, and seeds that are present in the soil are all destroyed by temperatures between 50 and 150 °C (Santin et al. 2016).

1.2.2. Physical Properties

Both soil chemical characteristics and soil physical characteristics have a significant impact on how plants

develop. Wildfire directly effects the physical characteristics of soil such as; appearance, volumetric density, pores, stability of aggregates, moisture content, and water absorption (Albalasmeh et al. 2013).

1.2.3. Chemical Properties

The loss of nutrients in soil texture, changes in soil chemistry, and availability of macronutrient and micronutrients and how fire affects the soil nutrients and chemically change it. Forest managers and ecologists are especially interested in these nutrients because they have the greatest potential to influence site productivity and vegetation dynamics (Boerner, 1982). They could be deposited, lost to the atmosphere, or as ash, may persist in debris from partially burned vegetation. Burnt soils have lower nitrogen, higher calcium, essentially unaltered levels of magnesium, potassium, and phosphorus, and very little amount or no potassium (Neff et al., 2005).

Area	Year	Effect of wildfire
New Mexico	2000	Burned about 420 dwellings, damaged >100 buildings \$1 billion damage.
Washington	2001	Killed 4 firefighters.
Colorado	2002	5 firefighter deaths, 600 structures fires.
California	2003	6 fatalities and 993 destroyed dwellings. related to the Cedar fire
Alaska	2004	largest wildfire in terms of area from 1997 to 2007.
California	2006	1 residence burned, no casualties.
Georgia	2007	Georgia's largest fires ever recorded. 26 buildings were destroyed.
North Carolina	2008	Lightning caused a peat fire to ignite on June 1 in North Carolina, which had the worst drought on record.
British Columbia	2009	This fire, also known as the Lava Canyon fire, was the biggest in British Columbia in 2009. This fire, which was started on July 31 by lightning, gained attention when it endangered a herd of wild horses. [8]
British Columbia	2010	2010's biggest fire in British Columbia led to alerts and orders for evacuation. 70,000 acres were burned in a day. [8]
Texas	2011	Over 1,500 homes were lost in the most destructive fire in Texas state history.
Oregon	2012	The biggest fire in Oregon in last150 years.
Arizona	2013	On June 30, 19 firefighters lost their lives.
Washington	2014	The greatest single wildfire in the history of Washington State was created when 4 separate fires combined. [17]
Washington	2015	The largest wildfire complex in Washington state history. [18]
Kansas and Oklahoma	2016	Largest wildfire in Kansas history. [20]
Montana	2017	By mid-September, rain and snow had it under control.
British Columbia	2018	According to early estimates, the 2018 wildfire season in British Columbia had the greatest overall burn area ever, surpassing the historic 2017 wildfire season. [21]
Colorado	2019	Started September.
Arizona	2020	Started June south of Phoenix.

Table No 1: Wildfire effect in different areas since 2001 to 2020

2. Economic impacts of forest fires:

It's critical to take into consideration how greatly wildfire & fire epidemics affect the budget as they posture a cumulative threat all over the world. Permitting to an investigation, over the course of two years, each additional day that a town is exposed to smoke from a forest fire diminishes wages by around 0.04% (Borgschulte, 2022). Wildfires cause economic damage across various sectors, causing wrinkle effects across large areas. A 2018 study assessed that California wildfires cost the US economy \$148.5 B, with 1/3 of fatalities approaching from beyond the border. (Nathan, 2022)

Like other natural disasters, wildfires have ambiguous effects on regional economies. For starters, despite

increasing wildfire losses, the US government still does not consider the majority of wildfires to be catastrophes. In accordance with information gathered by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration on catastrophes costing \$1 billion or more in the United States since the year 1980, wildfires only make up 6% of these catastrophes and 5.5% of their expenses. In the US, wildfires have become more frequent and severe, severely damaging populated areas. In 2018, the Camp Fire damaged 18,804 structures and claimed 85 lives. Eight of the top ten most expensive fires since 2017 have occurred. (Walls, 2023).

Figure 3: In the San Diego Region, a study illustrates its financial percentages among social sectors

2.1. Loss of property:

One of the most common concerns of wildfires is property loss and damage. The U.S. Wildfire service estimates that over 700 wildfires burn every year, consuming over 26,000 buildings and roughly 7 million hectares of property. Each year, central and neighborhood organizations collaborate to put out these fires. (Madaan, 2020)

The immediate economic effects of wildfires include property destruction, displaced residents, destroyed businesses, and losses to insurers. Large wildfires may result in an increase in local employment and salaries as fire conquest efforts, but they can also disrupt local labor markets due to differences in seasonal employment. (Nathan, 2022)

2.2. Loss of infrastructure:

Highways, communication infrastructure, electrical lines, and water supply systems are just a few examples of the infrastructure that can be damaged by wildfires. After a fire, many agencies and organizations must spend a lot of money on restoration in order to restore the most basic services. The maintenance, damage evaluation teams, field data gathering, repair or substitution of roads, railings, advertisements, electricity supply, bridges and landscaping are all responsibilities of state transportation departments. In order to fix infrastructure destroyed by a fire, utilities and connections must be repaired, and the tax payers are bearing the brunt of these costs. 2003 wildfires in San Diego caused \$147.3 million in economic impact, causing significant losses to infrastructure, including 3,200 convenience poles,

wire, converters, and other related apparatus. (Diaz, 2012).

2.3. Decreased tourism:

There is no denying that the tourism industry of a region that relies either entirely or partially on forest assets for its tourism activities suffers when wildfires occur in forests, in addition to the communities affected. In fact, the peak tourist season is in the summer, a time when previously mentioned meteorological conditions increase the risk of forest fires. Wildfire disasters consequently have a direct effect on tourism. For instance, the summer 2000 fires in Greece caused over 50% of reservations to be cancelled in 2001 (Scott and Lemieux, 2009). The rapid evacuation of the area and/or delay and cancellations of their arrival are two significant changes in tourist behavior that are caused by wildfires (Michael, 2007).

Wildfires not only have the potential to ruin tourist-friendly landscapes, but also run the possibility of forcibly evicting locals for a protracted period of time. Smog tends to discourage tourists and nature lovers from visiting provincial & national parks, which may have a big impact on other industries as well. In this manner, wildfire can harm the tourism sector, coffee, and various other industries. (Nathan, 2022).

2.4. Reduce agricultural productivity:

In recent decades, several regions of the world have recorded a rise in the incidence of wildfire and damaged land. The agricultural industry is susceptible to catastrophes and risks, such as degradation and abandonment brought on by forest fires in southern Europe and Greece. These catastrophes may obligate a negative consequence preceding the expansion of crops, bullocks, human health, aquaculture, and fisheries. Fires commonly strike Greece during the dry season, destroying crops like wheat, barley, and oats (Stougiannidou, 2020).

However, 75 percent of the land burned by wildfires in the US is not in a woodland, with a large portion of it being covered by prairies and farms. The lives of people who reside or work in fields are directly impacted by wildfires, as is the production of agriculture. (Powell, 2021).

2.5. Fighting forest fire can be very expensive:

Over the past ten years, the expense of combating wildfires has drastically escalated and now exceeds \$3 billion annually. This expense is mostly attributable to reduction services, which also involve protecting private property and urban areas. These services are provided by firemen from regional, state, and federal authorities. Given that 84% of private holdings in the West are close to woods that are prone to fire, there will likely be an increase in the safeguarding of private property and urban land. Permitting to the US Sector of Farming, manpower, machinery, and logistical requirements drive up the cost of private property firefighting by 50% to 95%. These expenses cover things like temporary restrooms, wholesome food, and influence and interpersonal connections. (Welch, 2022).

3. Long term perspective on forest fires and droughts:

In forest ecosystems, dryness increases the likelihood of fires occurring, but other abiotic and biotic stresses and disturbance collaborate with drought and wildfire to impact how effectively forest ecosystems function (McKenzie, 2009). In summer-dry areas, warming temperatures may worsen droughts and low fuel moisture levels, which could alter the probability of fires. Geographical variability is impacted by seasonal timing of precipitation, which is influenced by previous fire patterns, ecological responses, and administration. The likelihood and effects of fires may alter as a result of factors like fuel generation and flammability. (Cook et al., 2014)

There are two competing effects of drought on vegetation, the fuel for wildfires. Drier vegetation is more likely to catch fire because drought regulates the wetness gratified of both living and departed vegetation. Summer drought in Nevada does not increase the risk of fire in grassland and herbaceous ecosystems. Heavy vegetation, such as bushes and trees, begins to dry out when drought lengthens or gets worse, increasing the risk of fire in forest and woodlands. On the other side, a drought may reduce the quantity of fuel that is available for burning, which would inhibit the growth of fast-growing shrubs, herbs, and grasses. Long droughts prevent plants in Nevada habitats from growing, which lowers the possibility of fire. However, due to long-term fuel

storage, drought does not dramatically reduce fuel in forests. (Davis, 2022).

Figure 4: Wildfires' drought responses based on physical mechanisms

4. Solutions

Preventing techniques

A variety of scientific disciplines and principles are used in the theoretical foundation for wildfire detection and monitoring. A few essential components are remote sensing, data analysis, modelling or mapping system for how fire behaves and spreads.

For accurate detection and monitoring, it is essential to comprehend how fires behave and propagate. Studying heat transmission, combustion, and fire dynamics are some examples of the physical characteristics of fire that are involved in this. Scientists and professionals can create more precise detection and monitoring techniques by understanding how flames start, spread, and interact with their surroundings.

Figure No 6: Preventing Techniques for the Solution of Wildfire

4.1. Remote sensing

Re risk mapping, re detection and monitoring, damage assessment, and post-re recovery planning are some of the data requirements for re management. Remote sensing is necessary for effective management. (Sunar, F., Kaya,et.al,1997) ellite remote sensing provides a cost-effective and efficient option for continuously and regularly observing forest dynamics at regional and global scales, as well as detecting forest disturbances and mapping forest changes (i.e. post-fire study). (Chen et al. 2014; Sunar et al. 2017).

In remote sensing the images captured from satellites’ devices digital image processing methods were applied to the images before and after the forest fire like:

- Spectral profile analysis
- Vegetation indices

In addition to the conventional maximum likelihood classification approach, a multilayer feed-forward neural network design was applied for comparison and efficacy study. The main ways are

- Study area
- Data collection
- Raster data and vector data

4.2. Mapping System

it was shown that a single remote sensing dataset cannot completely cover the entire impacted area while still meeting accuracy standards. Studies on the mapping of forest fire danger zones frequently employ GIS data. In Turkey's Manisa province, a mapping analysis of the forest fire danger zones that relies on remote sensing and GIS data was carried out (Golchin and Denis (2020).

The vegetation covers; The vegetation of that area tells that which vegetation cover cause fire like in Turkey Pine trees make up the majority of the forest's 23% total area, along with other green species and groups of bushes.

- Topography
- Land cover
- Distance from settlement

4.3. Pre-disaster planning and models prediction

A fire will burn more easily the lower the relative humidity is. Air temperature has a greater direct impact on fire than any other component, making it the most significant factor affecting fire behaviour. Wind enhances the oxygen supply, which helps fires burn. Additionally, air pressure propels sparks onto

fresh fuel. Rain, temperature wind and humidity helps to predict forest fire in relative area.

After Amasya Region, Antalya Region has Turkey's second-largest forest with area at 1,146,062 ha, or 60.43% of country's total land area (Forest Statistics 2015)

Used were the daily, monthly, and seasonal fire data as well as the daily, monthly, and seasonal data for the Antalya region from 2001 to 2014. The forestry department General Directorate provided the fire statistics, and the General Directorate from Meteorology provided the weather information. The frequency of fires and the burned area were chosen as important factors. The resulting equations explain about 65% of the variation in the frequency of fires and 62% of the variation in the burned area.

4.4. Artificial intelligence and machine learning

Machine learning is used to analyse photos of the Earth's surface that show places that are prone to wildfires. The purpose of this essay is to demonstrate how the combination of AI with detection technology, such as satellites, has the potential to fundamentally alter how we anticipate, deal with, and recover from wildfire occurrences.

Artificial intelligence enables the atmosphere and environment to function for its own safety. As a result, the environment evolves into an intelligent one, or more specifically. Machine learning helps in reacts quickly to efficient changes and warns relevant personnel in real time for environment and forests, allowing them to take appropriate action to prevent further decline. (Stipanicev, D. et al)

4.5. Educational efforts:

➤ The Mediterranean woods have evolved into a very complex system that is always changing and necessitates a particular form of proper management due to weather, forest structure, varieties of plant, and human activities over ages.

➤ In addition to affecting the growth conditions of Mediterranean forests, climate change would also have a significant impact on disturbance patterns, particularly those associated with extended hotter and drier spells that could become more frequent in some areas.

➤ Encourage organizations and teams to support the Fire Management Voluntary Guidelines' implementation.

➤ Promote good practises exchange programmes, provide risk assessment voluntary guidelines, risk mapping with an acceptable geographical and temporal resolution, and voluntary recommendations for preventive.

6. Policies

The major fire problem has been linked to drought and fire exclusion laws. However, it is possible to link a number of high-impact mega fires to land management purposes that led to dense forest conditions with high fuel and biomass accumulations in substantial area .Thus policies are required to manage the problem. Environmental conservation to oversee the restoration and enhancement of forests for their protective effects, particularly with regard to soil and water conservation.

The best measures to lessen your risk of a fire include protecting your roof and home from flying embers, using fire-resistant materials when building, establishing a fire-resistant perimeter around your home, and paying close attention to the types of plants and materials in your neighborhoods (Climatic check book).

"Adaptive strategies include options for resistance (preventing effects and safeguarding highly valuable resources), options for resilience (improving ecosystems) and options for response .In the future, it will be more crucial than ever to use priority-setting techniques (like triage), which are ideal for rapidly changing conditions and circumstances where needs outweigh the capacity to respond (Millar_CI_Stephenson_NL_Stephens)

7. The Role of Technology in Mitigation for Droughts

7.1 Satellite Technology for drought forecast: Evaporative Stress Index (ESI):

ESI was laid out as another dry season file in which vaporization is contrasted with potential in evapotranspiration utilizing satellite information. ESI addresses normalized irregularities in standardized clear-sky evapotranspiration proportion where a reference scaling motion is utilized to limit the effects of non-dampness related drivers. (Dong-Hyun Yoo et al 2020).

The ESI depends on the remote sensing model air trade backwards. The ALEXI processes, ESI through a

two-source balance model laid out by Reference or factors (e.g., dissemination, and sun-based gauges) are viewed as in the warm picture gained through this functional natural satellite. ET informational collections determined are obtained and created every day. (Dong-Hyun Yoo et al 2020).

7.2. Drought Monitoring for early Warning Systems in Romania:

Romanian Government is helped with taking choices on dry spell, land corruption and desertification issues by the interdisciplinary Public Panel to Battle Dry season, Land Debasement and Desertification, which is a consultative body. This Board of trustees is composed by The Service of Farming and Provincial Turn of events. The Public Meteorological Organization (NMA) is one of the three foundations that team up with the Specialized Secretariat of the Public Board of trustees to Battle Dry season. (National Meteorological Administration et al. 2013). The NMA is answerable for doing the weather conditions gauges and admonitions as well as functionally scatter them to decisional elements and all end-clients. The Public Meteorological Perception Organization inside the NMA incorporates 7 Provincial Meteorological Focuses (RMC). Romanian agrometeorological perception organization of NMA gives week by week in-situ observing and data are gathered, dissected and ordered by the Argo-meteorological Assistance. (National Meteorological Administration et al. 2013).

7.3. Remote Sensing Methods for Drought Monitoring:

Propels in remote detecting and related files (calculations) give an elective wellspring of information. These records are gotten from satellite-based infrared, uninvolved microwave, and spaceborne precipitation radar information. Dry spell conditions can be recognized by utilizing a dry season list, which evaluates the impact of dry season, as well as force, term, seriousness, and spatial degree of dry season. (Trisha Deevia Bhaga et al. 2020).

Surface water bodies can be distinguished. Optical sensing radiations are utilized to compute the distinctions between phantom groups, and sensors are reliant upon the impression of water top land comparative with encompassing area surfaces,

nonetheless, return signs should be decreased by waves on the water top land. (Trisha Deevia Bhaga et al. 2020).

We have numerous strategies to remove surface water bodies from remote detecting symbolism, in view of the rule of contrasting the low level of coefficient of reflection of water with land cover with a higher reflectance. Water files can be utilized to remove water top bodies, and determined from at least two groups, to recognize dry or wet lands.

(Trisha Deevia Bhaga et al. 2020).

8. The Role of Technology in Mitigation for Forests

8.1 Agroforestry Database:

Agroforestry, characterized as the conscious developing of trees or bushes on horticultural terrains, is getting a lot of consideration in the US from scholastic and government establishments. Agroforestry frameworks are viewed as an elective asset the board framework with potential to intercede a portion of the issues related with current rural turn of events and practices, for instance, soil disintegration, natural defilement, monetary crumbling of family ranches, and loss of woods assets and untamed life living space. It is generally contended that agroforestry can contribute towards reasonable agribusiness by limiting sources of info and expenses, decreasing ecological effects, and giving extra financial advantages to ranchers. A sum of five significant kinds of agroforestry frameworks have been recognized for the district.

- 1) Cropping.
- 2) Windbreaks.
- 3) Clavipectoral.
- 4) Buffers.
- 5) Farming of forest.

(Williams et al. 1997).

8.2 A Web-Based Application used for forestry Planning:

Agroforestry is at present being advanced in the US play land use methodology can give extra items, pay ecological, preservation advantages. For viable Forest arranging, expansion specialists require data on expected tree and bush parts as well as geographic data for explicit locales. The Southeastern Agroforestry Choice Emotionally supportive network (SEADSS) is

an electronic application being created to help landowners and expansion specialists in the US assess expected locales and reasonable plants and bush species for forestry arranging.

SEADSS provide on-line admittance to province level for spatial data, for example, geography, water science, soil science and land science physically use, which are fundamental in assessing potential forestry destinations and reasonable species. SEADSS joins a geological data framework part with a subtropical tree/bush data set, which empowers the client to inquiry for biophysically reasonable and monetarily and authoritatively helpful trees and bushes. Species determination is accomplished through Organized Inquiry Language questions that are known, executed utilizing Dynamic Server Pages.

At the point when the end client chooses a district and area of interest, environment and soil boundaries are passed to the data set and inquiries select the trees and bushes that fulfill the biophysical boundaries. Besides, the client can limit the quest for proper species by choosing specific administration, proliferation, item and administrations rules inside the electronic application. Tree and bush species outcome data are linked permitting the client to see extra species-explicit data including admittance to records and photos. The SEADSS model was at first tried by Alachua Region, Florida expansion specialists and will go through an intensive testing and assessment stage with a gathering of Northwest and Focal Florida expansion specialists. In view of suggestions from designated end clients, SEADSS will be refreshed and extended to give a productive agroforestry expansion and arranging apparatus. (Ellis A. et al., 2005).

8.3 Evaluation of a Low-Cost Tree-Ring System:

The system of tree-ring detecting framework contains a holder, sensors, and a few digital parts. The holder is construct by and can be changed in accordance with different sizes. An acrylic plate is put on the finish of a stick, which fills in as a hindrance and this is put on the storage compartment. Two pieces of the holder are movable; right off the bat, the stick can be utilized to change the interval between the plants and the acrylic plate, and furthermore the place of the sensor can be adjusted to agree with the center of the tree.

The detecting framework comprises of an ultrasound, GPS, microcontroller, ongoing clock, Wi-Fi safeguard, secure computerized (SD) card safeguard,

and show. All parts are fueled by an outer power bank through an all-inclusive sequential transport. The Arduino controls all parts and saves information on the SD card empowering move of gathered information to an Android telephone through Wi-Fi. The Bluetooth association with an Android telephone has recently been considered. (G Kitic et al., 2019).

9. Conclusion

A natural disaster like drought can be devastating and result in death. Drought influences fire extent, severity, degree, and frequency by interacting with timber output, geography, wildfire weather, and management actions. During drought circumstances, trees and grasses, which are popular wildfire fuels, may become drier and more flammable. Forest fires have both short and long term impacts on environment and economy. They cause air pollution, soil erosion and loss of biodiversity. It damages aquatic life, atmosphere and terrestrial environment by major pollutants. It destroys the biological physical and chemical properties of soil. It triggers climate change that ultimately increase the rate of droughts. Wildfires also contribute a lot in loss of economy all over the world. In 2018, the Camp Fire damaged 18,804 structures and claimed 85 lives. Eight of the top ten most expensive fires since 2017 have occurred. It also effects agriculture which is a backbone of many agrarian countries. There are many important preventive techniques and policies to tackle with wildfires and their impacts more efficiently. Technology plays a vital role in mitigation of forest fires because it is an alarming issue all over the world. Remote sensing and GIS mapping is used widely where we do models prediction, pre disaster planning and machine learning. Educational efforts and public awareness also play a vital role in mitigating forest fires.

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